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Prioritization and Comparison of Factors Affecting Occupational Accidents in Manufacturing Sector Using Interval Valued Pythagorean Fuzzy Sets

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ABSTRACT

The rise in industrial activities has led to an increase in occupational accidents, which significantly impact employee health and the sustainability of businesses. Currently, around 270 million occupational accidents occur annually. Therefore, occupational safety applications are of great importance. Conventional risk assessment techniques frequently neglect to evaluate intricate, multidimensional, and uncertain occupational safety factors, which leads to underestimating their significance. For this reason, the objective of the study is to identify and prioritize the factors influencing occupational accidents in the manufacturing sector to mitigate such incidents. For this purpose, the factors influencing occupational accidents are classified into five sub-categories: human factors, management factors, process factors, machinery/equipment factors, and environmental factors. To better represent uncertainty, data from five different experts were analyzed with the Interval-Valued Pythagorean Fuzzy Analytical Hierarchy Process (IVPF-AHP) method. The relationships between the Interval-Valued Pythagorean Fuzzy DEMATEL (IVPF-DEMATEL) and the factors influencing occupational accidents are elucidated. The findings identify which factors are more important in occupational safety strategies and provide an innovative approach to decision makers in an uncertain environment like occupational safety.

1 INTRODUCTION

Occupational accidents, which have increased with the increase in industrialization activities, not only endanger the health of employees but are also seen as one of the most important problems affecting the sustainability of businesses. According to the International Labour Organization's "A Call for Safer and Healthier Working Environments" report, published in 2023, more than 395 million workers worldwide suffered non-fatal workplace accidents, and an additional 2.93 million workers lost their lives as a result of a work-related cause [1]. Despite the fact that working conditions are evolving and changing as technology advances, the high number of non-fatal and fatal occupational accidents demonstrates the importance of occupational safety. Workplace accidents are caused by a

variety of factors, including carelessness, unsafe behavior, and failure to use personal protective equipment, due to human error; insufficient training and supervision due to management error; a lack of work standards, workload, process complexity and workflow issues due to process error. The manufacturing sector, on the other hand, is distinguished by complex processes, fast-paced work environments, a large workforce, and a diverse range of equipment, machinery, and equipment. Therefore, it is a sector with high occupational safety risks and a critical need for occupational safety services. As a result, the purpose of this research is to prioritize the factors that contribute to occupational accidents in the manufacturing sector and to examine the relationships between these factors. While traditional multi-criteria decision-making assumes that criteria and weights can be expressed with crisp values, serious practical issues arise in decision-making situations because the uncertainty inherent in real-life problems and information is ignored [2]. In this direction, fuzzy set theory was introduced alongside traditional set methods. The theory, proposed by Zadeh [3] in 1965, is based on the concept of the degree to which elements of a set belong to it. Later, Type-2 Fuzzy Sets were proposed by Zadeh [4] in 1975, Intuitive Fuzzy Sets by Atanassov [5] in 1986, Neutrosophic Sets by Smarandache [6] in 1998, Pythagorean Fuzzy Sets by Yager [7] in 2013, Spherical Fuzzy Sets by Kutlu Gündoğdu and Kahraman [8] in 2019 and Fermatean Fuzzy Sets by Senapati and Yager [9] in 2020. Pythagorean Fuzzy Sets are proposed as an extension of Intuitive Fuzzy Sets in order to provide decision makers with a wider range of expression and to provide a more flexible and powerful structure in handling uncertainty [10]. In the literature, PF-AHP and PF-DEMATEL can be used in most areas where multi-criteria decision-making techniques can be used, such as supply chain management [11], [12], performance or strategies evaluation [13], [14], risk factors and risk analysis [15], and the methods provide a better expression of uncertainty. Interval numbers are also used instead of crisp numbers to reduce uncertainty in decision-making [15]. In this study, Interval Valued Pythagorean Fuzzy AHP (IVP-AHP) and Interval Valued Pythagorean Fuzzy DEMATEL (IVPF-DEMATEL) methods were preferred in order not to lose information between the factors with high uncertainty and which have not been used before in the literature to determine the prioritization and relationships of the factors affecting occupational accidents in the manufacturing sector.

2 METHODOLOGY

The study aimed to identify and prioritize the factors affecting occupational accidents in the manufacturing sector in order to reduce occupational accidents. For this purpose, the factors and sub-factors affecting occupational accidents were determined and multi-criteria decision-making techniques, Interval Valued Pythagorean AHP and Interval Valued Pythagorean DEMATEL, were used.

2.1 Occupational Accidents Factors in Manufacturing Sector

To identify the factors that contribute to occupational accidents in the manufacturing sector, three different occupational safety experts were consulted to determine the main criteria and sub criteria. Five major categories were identified: human factors, equipment factors, environmental factors, administrative factors, and process factors. Human factors are elements derived from employees' individual characteristics, psychological, physical, and cognitive states. These factors directly influence an individual's attention, knowledge, mood, and behavioral patterns. The sub-criteria are classified into seven categories: fatigue, lack of attention, lack of education, psychological state, physiological state, sociocultural state, and unsafe behavior. Equipment factors include the physical condition and dependability of machinery, tools, automation systems, and technical equipment. Maintenance processes, automation errors, equipment age, and technological elements such as sensors are among the other considerations. The sub-criteria are classified into five categories: malfunction (machine error), old equipment, lack of maintenance, automation errors, and sensor failure. Environmental factors refer to the physical conditions of the work environment. There are eight sub-criteria: noise, lighting, thermal comfort, vibration, hygiene (industrial cleaning and microbiological risks), radiation, area and floor, and air quality. Administrative factors include the

effects of work organization, supervision, management style, and administrative policies on employees. Their sub-criteria fall into seven categories: workload, shift order, education policies, lack of supervision, incentives and rewards, economic satisfaction, and management pressure. Lastly, process factors concern the design, standardization, and flowcharts of work processes. This scope includes evaluations of work execution methods, step clarity, and OHS compliance. Their sub-factors are divided into five categories: a lack of labor standards, process complexity, workflow issues, time pressure, and OHS compliance. The Table 1 includes explanations for each sub-criteria.

Table 1. Main Criteria and Sub Criteria Definition

Main Criteria	Sub Criteria	Definition
Human Factors (C1)	Fatigue (S1)	It's a condition in which physical or cognitive capacity is reduced as a result of excessive effort, repetitive jobs, or insufficient rest. Fatigue reduces attention span, produces perceptual errors, and increases reaction time, which raises operational hazards.
	Lack of Attention (S2)	It is an employee's failure to sufficiently focus on a task or to effectively use their cognitive resources in the presence of environmental distractions. This raises error rates and increases the risk of accidents, particularly in fast-paced or sensitive industrial operations.
	Lack of Education (S3)	It's a condition in which an employee lacks adequate theoretical knowledge and practical skills about work equipment, processes, and safety protocols. This shortcoming causes major neglect and errors, especially in machinery-related accidents and the usage of personal protective equipment.
	Psychological State (S4)	It's a condition when an employee's psychological state, such as stress, worry, sadness, or emotional exhaustion, impairs decision-making quality, risk perception, and self-regulation. These elements all contribute to an increase in risky conduct.
	Physiological State (S5)	It is a condition in which physiological characteristics such as sleep deprivation, hunger, chronic disease, dehydration, or pharmaceutical effects impair both physical and cognitive functions, threatening operational safety. It is a significant variable, particularly in shift work systems.
	Sociocultural Situation (S6)	It is a condition in which an employee's cultural beliefs, education level, native language, and social conventions all have an impact on their capacity to understand, absorb, and apply safety guidelines. This aspect can have a direct impact on safety communication in production facilities with a multicultural workforce.
	Unsafe Behavior (S7)	It is a condition that involves behavioral violations such as consciously or unconsciously not complying with the rules, not using personal protective equipment (PPE), and acting outside the process.
Equipment Factors (C2)	Malfunction (Machine Error) (S8)	It's a condition when a mechanical, electrical, or software problem causes machinery or equipment to fail. Unexpected power-ups (such as abrupt movements), production shutdowns, and accidents at work can all result from a malfunction. With fail-safe systems, the chance of an accident is especially high.
	Old Equipment (S9)	It's a condition where machines that are worn out, old, or technologically outdated cause security components to malfunction in addition to performing poorly. This leads to serious security flaws in systems that are unable to compensate for risk.
	Lack of Maintenance (S10)	It's a condition in which insufficient implementation of predictive or periodic maintenance methods raises the risk of system failure. Lack of maintenance reduces equipment life, increases the frequency of failures, and generates unexpected, hazardous circumstances for operators (MTBF – Mean Time Between Failure decreases).
	Automation Errors (S11)	It's a condition that occurs in industrial automation systems as a result of PLC programming errors, software/firmware updates, robotic route specification issues, or hardware failures. Such errors might cause loss of control and mishaps during human-machine interactions.
	Sensor Failure (S12)	It's a condition in which calibration mistakes, data loss, or physical damage to sensors used in process control or safety systems hinder the system from recognizing environmental hazards. This can lead to false warnings, delayed intervention, or failure to recognize unsafe situations.
Environmental Factors (C3)	Noise (S13)	It's a condition in which high noise levels, whether continuous or sudden, result in permanent hearing damage, increased cognitive strain, communication difficulties, and loss of attention. Noise, in particular, can disrupt the perception of warning systems, resulting in accidents.
	Lighting (S14)	It's a condition in which inadequate, excessive, or misdirected lighting affects visual performance and contrast perception. This increases error rates and causes misinterpretation, inability to discern, or visual overload, which can result in workplace mishaps. This is especially important on assembly lines and in hazardous equipment locations.
	Thermal Comfort (S15)	It's a condition in which workers who operate in extremely hot or cold surroundings suffer from thermal stress, extended reaction times, distraction, and musculoskeletal difficulties. Exceeding thermal comfort levels presents extra obstacles, especially when utilizing personal protection equipment.
	Vibration (S16)	It's a condition in which continuous vibration from handled equipment or the ground results in musculoskeletal illnesses such as Hand-Arm Vibration Syndrome (HAVS) and Whole Body Vibration. Vibration can also impair motor abilities, limiting the operator's ability to manage the machine.
	Hygiene (Industrial Cleaning and	It's a condition in which failure to maintain proper workplace cleanliness raises the danger of exposure to biological agents (microorganisms, fungi, viruses, etc.), contamination, and occupational illnesses.

	Microbiological Risks (S17)	
	Radiation (S18)	It's a condition in which uncontrolled exposure to ionizing (X-ray, gamma, etc.) and non-ionizing (UV, microwave, RF) radiation sources causes cellular damage, immune system suppression, and carcinogenic effects over time.
	Area and Floor (S19)	It's a condition in which a workspace is not ergonomic, passageways are narrow, and floors are slippery or uneven, resulting in accidents such as falls, trips, or collisions. These types of accidents are among the most common lost-time injuries in the manufacturing industry.
	Air Quality (S20)	It is a condition in which airborne pollutants such as particulate matter, VOCs (volatile organic compounds), dust, and chemical gases have acute or long-term effects on the respiratory system. Deteriorating air quality can also cause distraction and decision-making errors by impairing perception.
Administrative Factors (C4)	Workload (S21)	It's a condition in which employees are assigned work that exceeds their capacity, either in quantity or duration, resulting in physical and cognitive fatigue, burnout, and a decrease in attention span. Excessive workload causes delayed reaction times, a tendency to complete tasks quickly but incorrectly, and risky work habits.
	Shift Order (S22)	It's a condition in which long, night, or irregular shifts disrupt employees' circadian rhythms, resulting in sleep disturbances, attention deficits, and increased psychophysiological stress. Shift work raises the risk of accidents, particularly in hazardous, operator-based jobs.
	Education Policy (S23)	It's a condition in which the frequency, timeliness, and effectiveness of OHS-focused training have a direct impact on employees' ability to identify hazards, assess risks, and implement appropriate interventions. Weak training policies stifle the growth of a corporate safety culture.
	Lack of Supervision (S24)	It's a condition in which failure to conduct sufficiently frequent and comprehensive workplace inspections results in violations of safety procedures and the adoption of informal (inappropriate) practices as the norm. The lack of inspections causes an increase in the number of accidents, particularly those involving behavior.
	Incentives and Rewards (S25)	It's a condition in which failure to incentivize and reward safe behaviors reduces employee motivation and causes unsafe behaviors to be ignored. Systems that lack positive reinforcement jeopardize the sustainability of a safety culture.
	Economic Satisfaction (S26)	It's a condition in which low pay, a lack of benefits, or job insecurity reduces an employee's sense of dedication and responsibility. This can lead to risky behaviors based on the principle of minimum effort, as well as violations of rules regarding equipment and PPE use.
	Management Pressure (S27)	It's a condition in which upper management puts intense pressure on employees to meet deadlines, production targets, or cost constraints, causing them to become stressed, work quickly but carelessly, and skip procedures. This type of pressure leads to a culture that prioritizes production over prevention.
Process Factors (C5)	Lack of Labor Standards (S28)	It's a condition in which the absence of clear, written, and widely disseminated procedures for how, when, and by what method operational tasks should be performed results in variations in practice among employees and the use of unsafe alternative methods. This raises the risk of accidents caused by substandard work.
	Process Complexity (S29)	It's a condition in which production processes are overly complex, intertwined, or functionally ambiguous, making it difficult for employees to understand them properly. This increases cognitive load, errors, and security protocol violations, particularly among new employees.
	Workflow Issues (S30)	It's a condition in which errors in task sequencing, ambiguities in priorities, or a failure to optimize transitions between process steps cause disorganization and synchrony loss in the workflow. Such structural incompatibilities can result in unexpected interventions, conflicts, and a stop-and-start effect, which can lead to occupational accidents.
	Time Pressure (S31)	It's a condition in which employees are under pressure to complete tasks within a specific time frame, they tend to make intuitive decisions rather than relying on cognitive control. This leads to risky behaviors such as skipping procedures, not wearing PPE, and operating equipment incorrectly.
	OHS Compliance (S32)	It's a condition in which processes and equipment design are not properly analyzed or optimized in accordance with OHS requirements, resulting in an inability to systematically control hazardous situations. This deficiency is especially noticeable in systems where analyses such as inherent safety, LOPA, and HAZOP are not implemented.

2.2 Pythagorean Fuzzy Sets

Pythagorean fuzzy sets, which are extensions of intuitionistic fuzzy sets proposed by Yager in 2013, define the type of fuzzy set in which the sum of the degrees of membership and non-membership to each element in a universe is equal to or less than one, as seen in Equation 1 [7], [16].

$$\mu^2 + \nu^2 \leq 1 \quad (1)$$

For interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy sets, which are a generalization of the Pythagorean fuzzy set and whose membership degrees are defined as an interval, the formula in Equation 1 must also be

satisfied. That is, the sum of the squares of the lower and upper bounds must be 1 or less than 1, as seen in Equation 2 [17], [18].

$$\sup (\mu^2) + \sup (v^2) \leq 1 \quad (2)$$

2.2.1 Interval Valued Pythagorean Fuzzy Analytical Hierarchy Process (IVPF-AHP)

AHP, based on the pairwise comparison method, was proposed by L. Saaty in early 1970s. [19]. The steps of Interval-Valued Pythagorean Fuzzy AHP (IVPF-AHP) are given below [15], [20]:

Step 1: Create a pairwise comparison matrix $R = (r_{jt})_{m \times m}$ based on the scores received from experts in line with the linguistic term shown in the table.

Table 2. Linguistic Terms for IVPFS-AHP

Linguistic terms	μ_L	μ_U	v_L	v_U
Certainly low importance (CLI)	0.00	0.00	0.90	1.00
Very low importance (VLI)	0.10	0.20	0.80	0.90
Low importance (LI)	0.20	0.35	0.65	0.80
Below average importance (BAI)	0.35	0.45	0.55	0.65
Average importance (AI)	0.45	0.55	0.45	0.55
Above average importance (AAI)	0.55	0.65	0.35	0.45
High importance (HI)	0.65	0.80	0.20	0.35
Very high importance (VHI)	0.80	0.90	0.10	0.20
Certainly high importance (CHI)	0.90	1.00	0.00	0.00
Equal importance (EE)	0.1965	0.1965	0.1965	0.1965

Step 2: Create the Differences Matrix using the formulas in Eq 3 and Eq 4.

$$d_{ij_L} = \mu_{ij_L}^2 - v_{ij_U}^2 \quad (3)$$

$$d_{ij_U} = \mu_{ij_U}^2 - v_{ij_L}^2 \quad (4)$$

Step 3: Calculate the Interval Multiplicatetive Matrix $S = (s_{ij})_{m \times m}$ using the Eq 5 and Eq 6.

$$s_{ij_L} = \sqrt{1000^{d_{ij_L}}} \quad (5)$$

$$s_{ij_U} = \sqrt{1000^{d_{ij_U}}} \quad (6)$$

Step 4: Calculate the indeterminacy value $H = (h_{ij})_{m \times m}$ using Eq 7.

$$h_{ij} = 1 - (\mu_{ij_U}^2 - \mu_{ij_L}^2) - (v_{ij_U}^2 - v_{ij_L}^2) \quad (7)$$

Step 5: Determine unnormalized weights using indeterminacy value and multiplicative matrix $T = (\tau_{ij})_{m \times m}$ use Eq 8.

$$\tau_{ij} = \left(\frac{S_{ijL} + S_{ijU}}{2} \right) \cdot h_{ij} \tag{8}$$

Step 6: Find the priority weights w_i by using Eq 9.

$$w_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^m w_i}{\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^m w_{ij}} \tag{9}$$

2.2.2 Interval Valued Pythagorean Fuzzy DEMATEL (IVPF-DEMATEL)

DEMATEL is a method developed in 1974 by the Science and Human Relations Program of the Battelle Memorial Institute in Geneva, which, unlike traditional multi-criteria decision-making techniques, determines the interdependencies between factors using structural modeling and causal diagrams [21]. The steps of IVPF-DEMATEL are shown below [22]:

Step 1: Create the initial decision matrix $A = (a_{ij})_{m \times m}$ based on the scores received from the experts according to Table 3.

Table 3. Linguistic Terms for IVPFS-DEMATEL

Linguistic terms	μ_L	μ_U	ν_L	ν_U
Very High Influence (VHI)	0,80	0,95	0,00	0,10
High Influence (HI)	0,60	0,80	0,10	0,30
Low Influence (LI)	0,40	0,60	0,30	0,50
Very Low Influence (VLI)	0,20	0,40	0,50	0,70
Low Influence	0,00	0,20	0,70	0,90

Step 2: Create the crisp direct relationship matrix $B = (d_{ij})_{m \times m}$ by defuzzifying the initial decision matrix (A). First, calculate the hesitancy degree of the lower and upper points using Eq 10 and Eq 11. Then, defuzzify using Eq 12.

$$\pi^- = \sqrt{1 - (\mu_u^2 - \nu_u^2)} \tag{10}$$

$$\pi^+ = \sqrt{1 - (\mu_L^2 - \nu_L^2)} \tag{11}$$

$$DD(P) = \frac{\mu_L^2 + \mu_U^2 + (1 - \nu_L^2 - \pi^+) + (1 - \nu_U^2 - \pi^+) + \mu_L \mu_U + \sqrt{(1 - \nu_L^2 - \pi^+)(1 - \nu_U^2 - \pi^-)}}{6} \tag{12}$$

Step 3: Normalize the crisp direct relationship matrix $N = (n_{ij})_{m \times m}$.

$$N = S \times B \tag{13}$$

$$S = \min \left\{ \frac{1}{\min_{1 \leq i \leq m} \sum_j b_{ij}}, \frac{1}{\max_{1 \leq j \leq m} \sum_i b_{ij}} \right\}, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, m \tag{14}$$

Step 4: Create the total relationship matrix.

$$T = N(I - N)^{-1} \tag{15}$$

where I is an $n \times n$ identity matrix.

Step 5: Calculate the influence degree (D), influenced degree (R), centrality degree (D+R), and cause degree (D-R) using Eq 16 and Eq 17.

$$R = \left[\sum_{i=1}^n t_{ij} \right]_{1 \times n} \quad (16)$$

$$D = \left[\sum_{j=1}^n t_{ij} \right]_{n \times 1} \quad (17)$$

3 RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

The criteria weights were first determined using the IVPF-AHP method. The IVPF-AHP method involved consultation with five experts. Two of these experts were mechanical engineers with over ten years of experience, selected from professionals in the manufacturing sector, and three of them were industrial engineers and occupational safety specialists with over five years of experience in their respective fields. Expert scores were gathered using the Linguistic Terms in Table 1, and Table 4 displays the assessments that were obtained for the main criteria.

Table 4. Linguistic Terms for IVPF-AHP Method's Main Criteria

		C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
Expert 1	C1	EE	CHI	EE	AI	AI
	C2	CLI	EE	VHI	BAI	BAI
	C3	EE	EE	EE	BAI	BAI
	C4	AI	AAI	AAI	EE	VHI
	C5	AI	AAI	AAI	VLI	EE
Expert 2	C1	EE	HI	AAI	AAI	AI
	C2	LI	EE	BAI	AI	AI
	C3	BAI	AAI	EE	HI	AAI
	C4	BAI	AI	LI	EE	EE
	C5	AI	AI	BAI	EE	EE
Expert 3	C1	EE	HI	LI	LI	AI
	C2	LI	EE	VHI	VHI	VHI
	C3	LI	VLI	EE	LI	HI
	C4	HI	VLI	HI	EE	AAI
	C5	AI	VLI	LI	BAI	EE
Expert 4	C1	EE	VHI	HI	HI	EE
	C2	VLI	EE	AI	VLI	VLI
	C3	LI	AI	EE	EE	LI
	C4	LI	VHI	EE	EE	VLI
	C5	EE	VHI	HI	VHI	EE
Expert 5	C1	EE	VHI	VHI	HI	AAI
	C2	VLI	EE	HI	EE	EE
	C3	VLI	LI	EE	LI	LI
	C4	LI	EE	HI	EE	EE
	C5	BAI	EE	HI	EE	EE

The initial matrix was created by combining the scores with the interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy weighted average operator [17]. The difference matrices for the lower and upper differences were then created, as shown in Table 5 and Table 6, respectively.

Table 5. Lower Difference Matrix for IVPF-AHP's Main Criteria

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
C1	0	0,48	0,070288	0	-0,03514
C2	-0,72	0	0,22	-0,105432	-0,10543
C3	-0,246008	-0,44	0	-0,210864	-0,22
C4	-0,26	-0,035144	0,017572	0	-0,01514
C5	-0,105432	-0,035144	-0,04	-0,07572	0

Table 6. Upper Difference Matrix for IVPF-AHP's Main Criteria

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
C1	0	0,72	0,246008	0,26	0,105432
C2	-0,48	0	0,44	0,035144	0,035144
C3	-0,070288	-0,22	0	-0,017572	0,04
C4	0	0,105432	0,210864	0	0,07572
C5	0,035144	0,105432	0,22	0,015144	0

Next, as shown in Tables 7 and 8, the interval multiplicative metric (S) was created.

Table 7. Upper Interval Multiplicative Metric for IVPF-AHP's Main Criteria

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
C1	1	5,2480746	1,2747705	1	0,8856946
C2	0,0831764	1	2,1379621	0,6947875	0,6947875
C3	0,4275511	0,2187762	1	0,4827297	0,4677351
C4	0,4073803	0,8856946	1,0625711	1	0,9490389
C5	0,6947875	0,8856946	0,8709636	0,7698746	1

Table 8. Lower Interval Multiplicative Metric for IVPF-AHP's Main Criteria

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
C1	1	12,022644	2,3389019	2,4547089	1,439289
C2	0,1905461	1	4,5708819	1,1290573	1,1290573
C3	0,7844549	0,4677351	1	0,9411135	1,1481536
C4	1	1,439289	2,0715528	1	1,2989128
C5	1,1290573	1,439289	2,1379621	1,0536976	1

After creating the interval multiplicative metric (S), Indeterminacy Matrix H was created as seen in Table 9.

Table 9. Indeterminacy Matrix for IVPF-AHP's Main Criteria

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
C1	1	0,76	0,82428	0,74	0,859424
C2	0,76	1	0,78	0,859424	0,859424
C3	0,82428	0,78	1	0,806708	0,74
C4	0,74	0,859424	0,806708	1	0,909136
C5	0,859424	0,859424	0,74	0,909136	1

Finally, the unnormalized weights matrix shown in Table 10 was created to calculate the criteria weights.

Table 10. Unnormalized Weights Matrix for IVPF-AHP's Main Criteria

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
C1	1	6,5628732	1,4893389	1,2782423	0,9990733
C2	0,1040145	1	2,6164492	0,783728	0,783728
C3	0,4995162	0,2677394	1	0,5743128	0,5978788
C4	0,5207307	0,9990733	1,2641614	1	1,0218469
C5	0,783728	0,9990733	1,1133025	0,8289376	1

The 5 main criteria and 32 sub-criteria identified by the IVPF-AHP were weighted, and all procedures demonstrated for the main criteria were also applied to the identified sub-criteria. Table 11 shows the local and global weights of the main criteria and sub-criteria.

Table 11. IVPF-AHP Results

Main Criteria	Weights	Sub Criteria	Local Weights	Global Weights	Ranking
Human Factors (C1)	0,389494833	Fatigue (S1)	0,186878	0,072788	2
		Lack of Attention (S2)	0,14326	0,055799	5
		Lack of Education (S3)	0,250816	0,097692	1
		Psychological State (S4)	0,150332	0,058554	4
		Physiological State (S5)	0,069354	0,027013	15
		Sociocultural Situation (S6)	0,074228	0,028911	14
		Unsafe Behavior (S7)	0,125132	0,048738	7
Equipment Factors (C2)	0,181791991	Malfunction (Machine Error) (S8)	0,173994	0,031631	11
		Old Equipment (S9)	0,126612	0,023017	20
		Lack of Maintenance (S10)	0,282534	0,051362	6
		Automation Errors (S11)	0,243467	0,04426	8
		Sensor Corruption (S12)	0,173393	0,031521	12
Environmental Factors (C3)	0,101054478	Noise (S13)	0,080207	0,008105	31
		Lighting (S14)	0,255576	0,025827	18
		Thermal Comfort (S15)	0,081036	0,008189	30
		Vibration (S16)	0,086408	0,008732	28
		Hygiene (S17)	0,085819	0,008672	29
		Radiation (S18)	0,068078	0,00688	32
		Area and Ground (S19)	0,182104	0,018402	23
Administrative Factors (C4)	0,165217749	Air Quality (S20)	0,160771	0,016247	25
		Workload (S21)	0,26107	0,043133	9
		Shift Order (S22)	0,060529	0,01	26
		Education Policy (S23)	0,155384	0,025672	19
		Lack of Supervision (S24)	0,158624	0,026208	16
		Incentives and Rewards (S25)	0,058767	0,009709	27
		Economic Satisfaction (S26)	0,177576	0,029339	13
Process Factors (C5)	0,162440948	Management Pressure (S27)	0,128051	0,021156	21
		Lack of Labor Standards (S28)	0,223938	0,036377	10
		Process Complexity (S29)	0,160456	0,026065	17
		Workflow Issues (S30)	0,107404	0,017447	24
		Time Pressure (S31)	0,114139	0,018541	22
		OHS Compliance (S32)	0,394063	0,064012	3

According to Table 11, human factors have been identified as the most important factor causing occupational accidents in the manufacturing sector. Based on statistics published in Herbert William Heinrich's book from 1931 "Industrial Accident Prevention: A Scientific Approach," 88% of occupational accidents are said to be caused by unsafe behaviors [23]. Therefore, it makes sense that the most significant factor affecting occupational accidents is behavioral-based actions such as fatigue, lack of attention, and lack of education. When factors and sub-factors are taken into

consideration, the most important sub-criterion for the human factor (C1) is lack of education (S3); the most important sub-criterion for the equipment factor is lack of maintenance (S10); the most important sub-criterion for the environmental factor (C3) is lighting (S14); the most important sub-criterion for the administrative factor (C4) is workload (S21); and finally, the most important sub-criterion for process factors (C5) is OHS compliance (S32). While factors affecting work accidents such as lack of education, lack of maintenance, lighting, workload and OHS compliance are evident, it is noteworthy that the economics satisfaction criterion stands out among administrative factors affecting work accidents. Lack of education (S3) ranks first among factors contributing to occupational accidents in general, followed by fatigue (S1) and OHS compliance (S32). According to this finding, the fact that the first two factors influencing occupational accidents are human-related suggests that these incidents are highly preventable. The third criterion emphasizes the importance of designing processes in accordance with OHS. Although the primary goal of occupational safety services is to prevent danger and, if it cannot be avoided, to reduce exposure, shaping the process in accordance with OHS from the beginning is critical in reducing occupational accidents.

After prioritizing factors using the IVPF-AHP, the IVPF-DEMATEL method was applied to examine causal relationships between the criteria. First, scores were collected based on the linguistic terms in Table 3 from five occupational safety experts with 5+ years of experience in the field. The experts' linguistic evaluations are shown in Table 12.

Table 12. Linguistic Terms for IVPF-DEMATEL Method's Main Criteria

		C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
Expert 1	C1	EE	VHI	HI	HI	HI
	C2	HI	EE	HI	HI	HI
	C3	HI	VLI	EE	VLI	VLI
	C4	HI	VHI	VLI	EE	LI
	C5	HI	HI	LI	VHI	EE
Expert 2	C1	EE	VHI	HI	LI	LI
	C2	VHI	EE	HI	HI	HI
	C3	HI	HI	EE	LI	LI
	C4	VHI	VHI	LI	EE	LI
	C5	VHI	VHI	VLI	VHI	EE
Expert 3	C1	EE	HI	HI	VHI	HI
	C2	HI	EE	HI	VLI	HI
	C3	LI	HI	EE	LI	VLI
	C4	VHI	HI	VHI	EE	HI
	C5	VHI	LI	VLI	HI	EE
Expert 4	C1	EE	VHI	HI	HI	LI
	C2	VHI	EE	HI	VHI	LI
	C3	HI	LI	EE	HI	LI
	C4	HI	VHI	HI	EE	HI
	C5	HI	VHI	VLI	HI	EE
Expert 5	C1	EE	HI	HI	HI	HI
	C2	HI	EE	HI	HI	HI
	C3	VHI	LI	EE	HI	HI
	C4	VHI	HI	HI	EE	HI
	C5	VHI	HI	VLI	HI	EE

After the initial matrix was created, the crisp direct relationship matrix was created and normalized. Then total relationship matrix was created. Matrix for IVPF-DEMATEL shown in Table 13 and Table 14, respectively.

Table 13. Normalize Crisp Direct Relationship Matrix for IVPF-DEMATEL's Main Criteria

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
C1	0	0,1935437	0,2223568	0,1920241	0,1490756
C2	0,2500982	0	0,1955714	0,1621392	0,1001475
C3	0,1920241	0,0680859	0	0,1659602	0,0689445
C4	0,2789388	0,2147476	0,1323845	0	0,1365199
C5	0,2789388	0,1719288	-0,0354195	0,2500982	0

Table 14. Total Relationship Matrix for IVPF-DEMATEL's Main Criteria

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
C1	0	-0,0963402	-0,1072807	-0,1032004	-0,056039
C2	-0,1618475	0	-0,0891601	-0,0803816	-0,0328171
C3	-0,0943052	-0,0208896	0	-0,0674468	-0,0167637
C4	-0,1973723	-0,1136529	-0,0570805	0	-0,0515581
C5	-0,1900697	-0,083752	0,009839	-0,1420085	0

As a result, the influence degree (D), influenced degree (R), centrality degree (D+R), and cause degree (D-R) were calculated. The calculated values are shown in Table 15. Additionally, an influential diagram was created for the main criteria and their sub-criteria, shown in Figures 1, 2, respectively.

According to the IVPF-DEMATEL analysis results, if the cause degree (D-R) is positive, the factor is in the cause group; if negative, the factor is in the effect group. For the main criterion, human factors (C1) and environmental factors (C3) are in the cause group, while equipment factors (C2), administrative factors (C4), and process factors (C5) are in the effect group. The most central and most frequently occurring factor in the system was environmental factors (C3). The most influential and least central factor was human factors (C1). The most affected factor by others was process factors (C5). For the main criteria, human factor (C1) is seen as the most important cause of occupational accidents. Interventions in human factors significantly affect occupational accidents. Priority should be given to improvements in criterion C1. The factor with the highest centrality and position in the system was administrative factors (C3). Optimizing C3 improves the balance of the system but does not provide a solution. Process factors (C5) appears to be the strongest outcome in the system. Improvement can be achieved by improving the factors that affect it, not the process factor itself. Equipment factors (C2) and administrative factors (C4) are included in the system as intermediate effects and secondary results.

Among the human factors sub-criteria, fatigue (S1), lack of attention (S2), psychological state (S4), and unsafe behavior (S7) are included in the cause group, while lack of education (S3), physiological state (S5), and sociocultural situation (S6) are included in the effect group. Fatigue (S1) appears to be the strongest causal factor. Within the human factor, S1 is the first cause factor that requires intervention to prevent workplace accidents. While factors S2 and S4 do not have as much impact as S1, they contribute significantly to the occurrence of workplace accidents. S7, although at a lower level, is still included in the cause group. While unsafe behavior is a very significant factor affecting workplace accidents, it may be considered a low cause because it is the result of many other factors. S3, S5, and S6 appear to be effect factors and are influenced by other factors. If meaningful results are to be obtained from the effects of these factors, interventions in these other factors are necessary.

Table 15. Results for IVPF-DEMATEL

	Influence Degree (D)	Influenced Degree (R)	Centrality Degree (D+R)	Cause Degree (D-R)	Cause/Effect	D+R Ranking	D-R Ranking
C1	-0,362860272	-0,643594818	-1,00645509	0,280734546	Cause	5	1
C2	-0,364206291	-0,314634729	-0,67884102	-0,049571561	Effect	3	4
C3	-0,199405355	-0,243682417	-0,443087772	0,044277061	Cause	1	2
C4	-0,419663856	-0,393037271	-0,812701128	-0,026626585	Effect	4	3
C5	-0,405991311	-0,157177851	-0,563169162	-0,248813461	Effect	2	5
S1	-1,869111344	-2,987578445	-4,856689789	1,118467102	Cause	7	1
S2	-0,489159281	-0,972779863	-1,461939144	0,483620582	Cause	2	2
S3	-0,942493855	-0,720559519	-1,663053374	-0,221934337	Effect	3	5
S4	-1,697290311	-2,10558257	-3,802872881	0,408292259	Cause	6	3
S5	-1,116666169	-0,787437671	-1,90410384	-0,329228498	Effect	4	6
S6	-1,889895779	-0,19226833	-2,082164109	-1,69762745	Effect	5	7
S7	-0,450740607	-0,689150948	-1,139891555	0,238410342	Cause	1	4
S8	-0,273730966	-0,578203956	-0,851934922	0,304472989	Cause	5	1
S9	-0,428631922	-0,089172516	-0,517804437	-0,339459406	Effect	2	5
S10	-0,498295229	-0,158990956	-0,657286184	-0,339304273	Effect	4	4
S11	-0,210442274	-0,381790267	-0,592232541	0,171347992	Cause	3	3
S12	-0,147776609	-0,350719306	-0,498495915	0,202942697	Cause	1	2
S13	-0,024406433	-0,268296568	-0,292703001	0,243890134	Cause	3	1
S14	-0,127822226	-0,230132482	-0,357954709	0,102310256	Cause	5	3
S15	-0,118813866	-0,152984	-0,271797865	0,034170134	Cause	1	4
S16	-0,131946205	-0,305325257	-0,437271462	0,173379052	Cause	7	2
S17	-0,339331458	-0,177706283	-0,517037741	-0,161625175	Effect	8	7
S18	-0,288634616	-0,051440666	-0,340075282	-0,23719395	Effect	4	8
S19	-0,218825111	-0,1601364	-0,378961511	-0,058688711	Effect	6	5
S20	-0,188758469	-0,092516729	-0,281275198	-0,09624174	Effect	2	6
S21	-0,973077078	-1,427130747	-2,400207825	0,454053669	Cause	7	1
S22	-0,440827633	-0,55346312	-0,994290753	0,112635487	Cause	5	3
S23	-0,51613719	-0,207413194	-0,723550385	-0,308723996	Effect	2	6
S24	-0,326766106	-0,465062607	-0,791828712	0,138296501	Cause	3	2
S25	-0,438563567	-0,408938525	-0,847502092	-0,029625043	Effect	4	5
S26	-0,365863954	-0,352676915	-0,718540869	-0,013187039	Effect	1	4
S27	-0,76182758	-0,408378001	-1,170205581	-0,35344958	Effect	6	7
S28	-3,541958379	-4,157263193	-7,699221572	0,615304814	Cause	2	2
S29	-4,413345315	-3,368028987	-7,781374302	-1,045316329	Effect	3	4
S30	-5,013007159	-4,166762316	-9,179769475	-0,846244843	Effect	4	3
S31	-5,705062123	-3,503828424	-9,208890548	-2,201233699	Effect	5	5
S32	-0,503262361	-3,980752418	-4,48401478	3,477490057	Cause	1	1

For the equipment factors sub-criteria, malfunction (machine error) (S8), automation error (S11), and sensor failure (S12) are in the cause group, while old equipment (S9) and lack of maintenance (S10) are in the effect group. Among the equipment factors, S8 appears to have the highest impact on occupational accidents. S11 and S12 are also present at significant rates, but not as much as S8. Factors S9 and S10 are in the effect group. While lack of maintenance and old equipment also cause occupational accidents, their indirect effects on machine failure, automation failure, and sensor failure, may have contributed to their inclusion in the cause group.

For the sub-criteria of environmental factors, noise (S13), lighting (S14), thermal comfort (S15), and vibration (S16) are in the cause group, while hygiene (industrial cleaning and microbiological risks) (S17), radiation (S18), area and floor (S19), and air quality (S20) are in the effect group. S13 and S16 appear to be the most important factors affecting occupational accidents. S14 and S15, although relatively weaker, are still significant in the occurrence of occupational accidents. S18 appears to be the most effected factor by other factors. S17, S19, and S20, although less effected, are in the effect category.

For the sub-criteria of the administrative factor, workload (S21), shift order (S22), and lack of supervision (S24) are in the cause group, while education policy (S23), incentives and rewards (S25),

economic satisfaction (S26), and management pressure (S27) are in the effect group. S21 appears to be the factor that most influences other factors. S24 and S22, while relatively less influential, are also among the factors affecting occupational accidents. S27 was the most affected factor. S23, S25, and S26, although relatively less affected, are still in the effect category.

Figure 1. Influential Diagram for IVPF-DEMATEL' Main Criteria

For the sub-criteria of the process factor, lack of labor standards (S28) and OHS compliance (S32) are in the cause group, while process complexity (S29), workflow issues (S30), and time pressure (S31) are in the effect group. S32 is considered one of the most fundamental and deep-seated structural triggering factors. While S28 also contributes significantly to workplace accidents, it is relatively less significant than S32. S31 is considered the most impacted factor. S29 and S30, although relatively minor, are in the effect group.

Figure 2. Influential Diagram for IVPF-DEMATEL's Sub Criteria

As a result of the research, the factors that influence occupational accidents were weighted and their relationships were examined. While the human factor appears to be the most influential in occupational accidents, lack of education, fatigue, lack of attention, and psychological state all play a role. It is worth noting that economic satisfaction ranks second only to workload in administrative factors. According to the findings, prioritizing training, fatigue management, and OHS compliance is critical for developing preventative strategies and building an OHS culture from the ground up.

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